

Optimization of coagulation-flocculation process for food industry waste water treatment using polyelectrolytes with inorganic coagulants

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Abstract : Food industry is a major source of waste water pollution. Several techniques are available to remove pollutants from food industry waste water. One of the promising technologies for the removal of pollutants from food industry waste water is coagulation and flocculation. In the present work, various coagulants like lime, alum and ferrous sulphate were applied on waste water to select the suitable one with optimum removal efficiencies for further treatment with polyelectrolytes. Parameters such as turbidity, Total suspended solids (TSS), Chemical oxygen demand (COD), Biological oxygen demand (BOD) and oil and grease content were evaluated. On the basis of results, lime was proven to be the most efficient inorganic coagulant for further treatment. It could remove 55.2% turbidity, 51% TSS, 49.6% COD, 51% BOD and 51% oil and grease at its optimum dosage of 50 mg/L. Generation of sludge in the coagulation-flocculation process was also studied. The volume of sludge was 22.5 mg/L at the optimum dosage of lime. Further cationic polyelectrolyte Organopol 5470C and anionic polyelectrolyte Chemfloc 430A were also studied in conjunction with lime. Organopol 5470C in conjunction with lime showed better result because of low dosage, maximum pollutant removal and minimum quantity of sludge generation. It could remove 94% turbidity, 95.5% TSS, 83.5% COD, 89% BOD and 92.5% oil and grease; whereas Chemfloc 430A in conjunction with lime could remove 91.2% turbidity, 90% TSS, 77.8% COD, 83% BOD and 86.8% oil and grease. The volume of sludge produced while using polyelectrolyte and lime together was much lower than using lime alone. The amount of sludge produced in case of Organopol 5470C and lime together is 8.9 mg/L, while sludge generation by Chemfloc 430A in conjunction with lime is 10.4 mg/L.

Keywords : Food industry waste water, coagulation, flocculation, polyelectrolytes, turbidity.

Introduction

The Indian food processing industry is one of the largest in the world in terms of production, consumption, export and growth prospects¹. The food industry in India is sunrise sector that has gained prominence in recent years. Mechanical lifestyle and crave for comfort is pushing people towards ready to eat service. Although it is good for progress of food industry but at the same time it leads to generation of waste water in tremendous volume during food processing. Large quantity of waste water is generated during rinsing and washing of the food products processed. Food industry waste water is one of the major sources of aquatic pollution since it contains high BOD, COD, TSS, turbidity and other pollutants^{2,3}. The effluent is toxic for aquatic life and exhibits strong mutagenic effects and physiological impairment^{4,5}. Conse-

quently, a new approach should be developed to force more stringent environmental regulation on the quality of effluent entering the receiving water.

The food industry waste water generally contains carbohydrates, inorganic and organic salts, oil, detergents, high concentration of protein and cleaning product⁶. These constituents give extra load on biological process; hence physicochemical treatment is needed to reduce the pollutants in food industry waste water⁷. Food industry waste water treatment method using zinc sulphate, ferrous sulphate, ferric chloride and alum has been reported extensively where reduction in COD by 66% is reported by alum dosage of 200 mg/L⁸. In food industry waste water 48.8% COD reduction at 450 mg/L dosage was reported by use of ferrous sulphate⁹. However, these methods suffer from limitations such as high dosages of inorganic

coagulants, large amount of sludge generation and high level of water mineralization¹⁰. Large amount of sludge generation due to use of inorganic coagulants becomes a major cost factor for sludge handling. Recently, use of polyelectrolyte as a flocculant for removal of pollutants in waste water has grown rapidly¹¹. Advancements in polymer chemistry have helped obtain polyelectrolytes with better purification efficiency through flocculation technology^{12,13}. Optimization of flocculants in industrial water is done by trial and error method due to availability of a large variety of polyelectrolytes and complex mechanism of the floc process. The main objective of present study is to investigate the flocculation efficiencies of cationic polyacrylamide Organopol 5470C and anionic polyacrylamide Chemfloc 430A in the treatment of food industry waste water in conjunction with inorganic coagulant. Both Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A are high charge density and high molecular weight polyacrylamide based polyelectrolytes. But the former is cationic while the latter one is anionic. Polyacrylamide has ability to remove large, dense, compact and stronger floc with good settling characteristics as compared to inorganic coagulants. It also reduces sludge volume to a larger extent. The flocculation performance depends on the type of flocculants and its molecular weight, ionic nature and type of waste water.

Results and discussion

The food processing waste water was analyzed. It was creamish white in colour and had bad smell. Water pH was slightly acidic in nature. So the pH was adjusted to 7 before start of the experiment. A lime dosage of 10 mg/L was required to neutralize the waste water. During the neutralization method, it was observed that it could not

only help to get the best pH range for further treatment but also in reduction in percentage of turbidity, COD, BOD, TSS and oil and grease. The raw waste water and neutralized waste water characteristics which was further used for the experiment is listed in Table 1. After the neutralization process, study on effectiveness of lime, alum and ferrous sulphate was carried out individually. Lime dosage was varied from 10 to 100 mg/L. At lime dosage of 50 mg/L, pH of the waste water increased to 7.7 with reduction in turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease by 55.2%, 51%, 49.6%, 51% and 51% respectively. At 75 mg/L of lime, the removal of oil and grease showed marginal improvement whereas turbidity, TSS, COD and BOD showed best result at 50 mg/L as indicated in Table 2. So it is evident from the result that 50 mg/L is the optimum dosage for further treatment. Alum dosage was used in the range of 10 to 100 mg/L as shown in Table 3. At the dosage of 75 mg/L, removal of turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease are 40%, 39%, 38%, 38.3% and 44.6% respectively. Beyond this dosage marginal improvement was observed only in oil and

Table 1. Characterization of raw and neutralized food processing industry waste water

Parameters	Raw waste water	Neutralized waste water
Colour	Creamish white	Creamish white
pH	6.1	7.0
Turbidity	410	250
TSS	1200	810
E.C.	1.70	1.60
COD	1021.6	825.5
BOD	655	418
Oil and grease	125.50	98.50

All values are expressed in mg/L except pH, colour, turbidity and E.C. The unit of turbidity is NTU and unit of E.C. is Ω^{-1} .

Table 2. Physicochemical treatment of food industry waste water using lime

Parameters	Neutralized waste water	Effluent concentration and coagulation dosages (mg/L)				
		10	25	50	75	100
pH	7.0	7.2	7.5	7.7	8.2	8.5
Turbidity	250	179	136	112	127	167
TSS	810.0	452.5	415.6	396.9	406.2	418.5
COD	825.5	525.0	478.8	415.5	453.0	482.0
BOD	418	315	298	205	247	315
Oil and grease	98.50	68.60	65.65	48.27	46.30	60.50
Volume of sludge	7.5	19.8	20.5	22.5	26.5	29.0

All values are expressed in mg/L except pH and turbidity. The unit of turbidity is NTU.

Table 3. Physicochemical treatment of food industry waste water using alum

Parameters	Neutralized waste water	Effluent concentration and coagulation dosages (mg/L)				
		10	25	50	75	100
pH	7.0	6.9	6.7	6.6	6.6	6.3
Turbidity	250	202	189	168	150	167
TSS	810	556.7	515.5	501.4	494.0	521.2
COD	825.5	630.5	602.6	545.5	512.0	525.5
BOD	418	368	312	290	258	263
Oil and grease	98.50	78.40	68.75	59.25	54.5	51.60
Volume of sludge	7.5	23.4	29.7	35.6	42.5	52.5

All values are expressed in mg/L except pH and turbidity. The unit of turbidity is NTU.

Table 4. Physicochemical treatment of food industry waste water using ferrous sulphate

Parameters	Neutralized waste water	Effluent concentration and coagulation dosages (mg/L)				
		10	25	50	75	100
pH	7.0	7.0	6.9	6.8	6.7	6.6
Turbidity	250	198	180	173	158	173
TSS	810.0	597.6	527.5	520.4	501.5	526.5
COD	825.5	653.5	618.5	567.0	526.5	537.5
BOD	418	398	345	302	269	289
Oil and grease	98.5	82.4	79.5	78.5	61.5	54.0
Volume of sludge	7.5	16.5	20.4	25.8	32.4	40.6

All values are expressed in mg/L except pH and turbidity. The unit of turbidity is NTU.

grease and its removal increased only by 3% at 100 mg/L. Alum addition alone did not result in efficient removal of turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease. It may be because food industry waste water is highly proteinous in nature and when alum combines with protein, it forms dense floc which does not settle easily.

In case of ferrous sulphate, removal was much lower than that of lime and alum. The result is listed in Table 4. At the dosage of 75 mg/L, removal of turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease were 36.8%, 38%, 36.2%, 35.6% and 37.5% respectively. At a higher dosage of 100 mg/L, only oil and grease removal showed increasing trend and was 45.2%. At the same time, sludge production was marginally less in volume as compared to the case of alum but more than in case of lime. Moreover, at higher dosage of ferrous sulphate dark colour was imparted to the effluent. Colour of effluent went on intensifying as the dosage increased. So treatment with ferrous sulphate was not very congenial to this waste water, considering colour and addition of iron content to the effluent.

It was observed that sludge production was affected

by dosage of inorganic coagulants. As the dosage of inorganic coagulant increased, the sludge volume also increased. The trend was similar in lime, alum and ferrous sulphate. Among the three, sludge volume was minimum in case of lime and maximum in case of alum.

A comparative study on the effectiveness of lime, alum and ferrous sulphate was done and it was found that lime was best suited inorganic coagulant for food industry waste water. The optimum dosage of lime was found to be 50 mg/L. Even sludge volume was found to be the least in case of lime as compared to alum and ferrous sulphate. So, lime dosage of 50 mg/L was adopted throughout the studies. In order to further decrease the percentage of turbidity, COD, BOD, TSS and oil and grease in waste water, Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A were used in conjunction with lime. The optimal dosage of flocculants was based on reduction of turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease.

Turbidity is a measure of light transmitting property in water with respect to colloidal and residual suspended matter. Colloidal matter scatters or absorbs light thus preventing its transmission. The turbidity of waste water

fluctuates according to TSS. The turbidity reduction in case of Organopol 5470C was more as compared to Chemfloc 430A as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The maximum removal of turbidity was 94% at dosage of only 1 mg/L with Organopol 5470C, whereas maximum removal with Chemfloc 430A was 91.2% at dosage of 2 mg/L.

Fig. 1. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on turbidity removal.

Fig. 2. Effect of Organopol 5470C on turbidity removal.

The efficiency of Organopol 5470C was impressive even at lower dosage. The percentage of TSS and turbidity removal showed the same trend. The TSS removal by Chemfloc 430A and Organopol 5470C are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. Organopol 5470C could remove 95.5% TSS at dosage of 1 mg/L, whereas Chemfloc 430A could remove 90% TSS at dosage of 2 mg/L. Both Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A are polyelectrolytes having high molecular weight and high charge density. It was observed that cationic polyelectrolyte was

Fig. 3. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on removal of TSS.

Fig. 4. Effect of Organopol 5470C on removal of TSS.

better in removal of turbidity and TSS. Organopol 5470C effectively coagulated the natural particulates and negatively charged colloidal material through charge neutralization, inter-particle bridging and hydrophobic flocculation. Charge neutralization was most effective factor in this food industry waste water treatment as compared to polymer bridging.

The percent removal of COD and BOD at various dosages was also studied. It was observed that the required dosage of Chemfloc 430A was slightly different than that for TSS and turbidity. The COD removal was 77.8% at 3 mg/L in Chemfloc 430A as shown in Fig. 5.

However, percent reduction of COD with Organopol 5470C was 83.5% even at very low dosage of 1 mg/L as shown in Fig. 6. Further increase in dosage did not im-

Fig. 5. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on removal of COD.

Fig. 6. Effect of Organopol 5470C on removal of COD.

prove reduction efficiency. This behaviour suggested that floc break up occurs due to charge reversal and dispersion when there is overdosing of flocculants. Fig. 7 shows that maximum removal of BOD with Chemfloc 430A is 83% with dosage of 3 mg/L, whereas Fig. 8 shows that Organopol 5470C could remove 89% BOD at 2 mg/L dosage. Figs. 9 and 10 show the removal percentage of oil and grease at different dosage of Chemfloc 430A and Organopol 5470C respectively. Result obtained in the lab studies showed that Organopol 5470C produced appreciable reduction in oil and grease at a higher dose as compared to other parameters. It may be because higher dose was required to break the emulsion.

Figs. 11 and 12 show the volume of sludge production when lime was used in conjunction with Chemfloc 430A and Organopol 5470C respectively. It was observed

Fig. 7. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on BOD removal.

Fig. 8. Effect of Organopol 5470C on BOD removal.

Fig. 9. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on oil and grease removal.

Fig. 10. Effect of Organopol 5470C on oil and grease removal.

Fig. 11. Effect of Chemfloc 430A on volume of sludge.

Fig. 12. Effect of Organopol 5470C on volume of sludge.

from the result that Organopol 5470C produced less sludge as compared to Chemfloc 430A. Therefore, it can be concluded that the amount of sludge produced depends upon type of polyelectrolyte, dosage applied and operating conditions. The result showed that the amount of sludge produced was the maximum when percentage of removal of TSS was highest in both cationic and anionic polyelectrolyte, although it was much lower as compared to the volume of sludge produced when lime was solely used. This behavior suggested that after the dosage of 1 mg/L of Organopol 5470C, as the dosage of cationic polyelectrolyte increased, the volume of sludge decreased. In case of Chemfloc 430A, after the dosage of 2 mg/L the vol-

ume of sludge decreased as dosage of polyelectrolyte increased.

Experimental

In this investigation, treatment studies were carried out on food products industrial effluent like ghee, butter, ice-cream, etc. Raw waste water was collected from food industry, situated in Faridabad (Haryana) and stored in a refrigerator so that it can be used for a longer period.

The waste water sample was analyzed for TSS and oil and grease content according to standard methods for the examination of water and waste water (Apha 1995)¹⁴. pH and electrical conductance was measured with the help of digital pH meter (Hanna HI 8314, USA) and digital conductivity meter supplied by Labtronix, India. Turbidity of waste water was measured with the help of digital nepheloturbidity meter. For COD estimation, digestion of sample was done in a COD reactor supplied by Hatch, USA followed by titration with standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. BOD values at 20 °C were estimated using dissolved oxygen meter.

Reagents :

Three different types of inorganic coagulants including lime, alum and ferrous sulphate were examined for their efficiencies. Alum, lime and ferrous sulphate were obtained from CDH (India) and their solutions were prepared in distilled water having concentration of 10 mg/L. Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A were used. Organopol 5470C was supplied by Ciba speciality chemicals and anionic polyelectrolyte Chemfloc 430A was supplied by Chemkimia.

Optimization of pH of water sample with lime :

The experiments were carried out using jar test apparatus. A conventional jar test apparatus, the Phipps and Bird six paddle stirrers with illuminated base, was used for jar test with 2 L square Plexiglas jar. All the tests were carried out with 1 litre sample of water in 2 litre jar. All the jars were filled with 1 litre of water and placed on each slot. Lime was added in each jar at varied dosages for optimization of pH for further treatment. The sample was agitated at 100 rpm for 1 min and later at 50 rpm for half an hour. After sedimentation for 30 min, supernatant liquid was drawn and pH as well as other impurities was determined.

Optimization of inorganic coagulants :

Neutralized waste water with pH 7 was further subjected to chemical treatment (second stage) using different conventional coagulants. A study on the effectiveness of lime, alum and ferrous sulphate was done individually. Lime was added in each jar at different dosages and agitated at 100 rpm for 1 min and later at 50 rpm for half an hour. After sedimentation, residual turbidity, TSS, COD, BOD and oil and grease were determined. The process was repeated with alum and ferrous sulphate individually.

Optimization of polyelectrolytes :

After studying effectiveness of lime, alum and ferrous sulphate individually, lime was found to be the most efficient inorganic coagulant in food industry waste water. So lime was used throughout the study in conjunction with polyelectrolyte. Lime was added in each jar at various dosages and agitated for one minute at 100 rpm. At this stage, the desired dosage of polyelectrolyte as a coagulant aid was added. It was observed that polyelectrolyte should be added after mixing of lime because poor performance was obtained when lime and polyelectrolyte were added simultaneously. It was in close agreement with Kapoor *et al.*¹⁵. The process was repeated with both Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A.

Conclusion

Understanding the nature of waste water is fundamental to design appropriate water treatment system. The variation in turbidity, COD, BOD, TSS and oil and grease make it difficult to handle. These pollutants cannot be removed by the use of inorganic coagulant only. Hence it is imperative to use coagulant aid like polyelectrolyte.

Keeping this in view, inorganic coagulant like lime, alum and ferrous sulphate were studied. Result indicated that among the three inorganic coagulants, lime showed best result at optimum dosage of 50 mg/L. So dosage of 50 mg/L lime was kept constant throughout the experiment. Organopol 5470C and Chemfloc 430A were used in conjunction with lime. Result indicated that cationic polyelectrolyte Organopol 5470C is more efficient as compared to anionic polyelectrolyte Chemfloc 430A. Result also indicated that combined use of lime and Organopol 5470C resulted in reduction of 60.4% in sludge produc-

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tion as compared to the case when lime was solely used. It is recommended that this technique can be implemented for the treatment of food industry waste water.

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